

ANALYSIS OF TOURISM TERMS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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Annotation

The article deals with the classification of tourism terms in English and Uzbek languages. As well as similarities between tourism terms are also considered.

Keywords

English tourism terms and terminology, classification of terms, terminology, terminology system, analysis.

Tourism terminology is widely used not only in the professional environment but also in other areas of speech communication, which is why the need to learn the language of tourism was born. The Tourism terminology is unique in that it stands out from other systems of terms. The analysis of tourism terms is also a necessary task. Because in this, various tourism systems are analyzed, and not the terms themselves. The lexical counterpart often does not evoke the correct idea of lexical unity, as the reciprocal terms in the two languages represent different concepts, or concepts that are close to each other but differ in that the scope of meaning is different. For example, in this regard, it is necessary, in our opinion, to carry out a comparative analysis of individual terms and implement ways to translate them from English to Uzbek or from Uzbek to English.

As a result of the reforms carried out in our country, significant progress has been made in comparative linguistics in terms of interpreting terminology as an independent field, testing the value, practical importance and viability of terms used in consumption. As a result, the priority of studies based on practical and terminological analysis, which reflects the possibility of using linguistic tools for this purpose and shows the individuality of the use of words, began to be observed. "It is an urgent task to preserve the purity of our national language in the conditions of globalization, to increase its vocabulary, to create an Uzbek

alternative to modern terms in various fields, and to ensure their uniform use" in English and Uzbek terminology. The need to analyze tourism terms, to rely on the advanced experience of world linguistics in elucidating their linguistic and culturological features, and to comprehensively research such issues as conciseness, comprehensibility, and compliance with international standards in the creation of new terminological systems is growing.

Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF5847 of October 8, 2019 "On approval of the concept of development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030", No. PF-6084 of October 20, 2020 "On measures to further develop the Uzbek language in our country and improve the language policy" , Decree No. PF-6165 dated February 9, 2021 "On measures to further develop domestic and pilgrimage tourism in the Republic of Uzbekistan", No. PQ-3775 dated June 5, 2018 "Increasing the quality of education in higher education institutions and their active participation in comprehensive reforms implemented in the country Decision of the Cabinet of Ministers dated August 11, 2017 No. 610 "On measures to further improve the quality of teaching foreign languages in educational institutions" and other regulatory legal documents related to the field thesis serve a certain level.

Many lexemes in the system of English tourist terms are already understandable without translation. However, the fact that our cultures belong to different language families leads to some linguistic inconsistencies. For example, the core of the lexeme "complimentary" in the term "complimentary ticket" should have given the meaning "takalluf" and its direct translation should be "takallufli". However, in the context of tourism, the combination of his participation (given above) turns into a "free ticket". The similar term "budget travel" is also translated as "cheap (pocket) travel", that is, the "budget" component in this combination loses its primary meaning. Sometimes a term that expresses a specific meaning in a foreign language is replaced by an alternative with a general meaning in the process of acquisition. We can observe this phenomenon in the "days of service" combination. It is more appropriate to adopt it in the form of "working days" and not "service days". This is also in accordance with the structure and language features of the Russian language used in everyday life in our country. After all, representatives of Russian-speaking culture also use this term in the form of "rabochie dni". Similarly, the term "ethnic food" is not "ethnic food", but "national food" in our language. If the initial form is accepted in a context foreign to our imagination, the later form has entered the sphere of ordinary everyday speech. There is also a cross-linguistic disparity in the expression of the concept of "hotel".

The term "guest house" in English tourism terminology differs from the traditional concept of "hotel" and has the following meanings: 1. a private boarding house intended only for regular residents of the area, providing them with accommodation and food/drinks; 2. A state hotel for official guests in the Far East.

The above expressions have a private character, and the lexeme "hotel" represents the concept of a modern hotel, which has a general character.

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